

Potentiometric Studies on La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Tb(III), Dy(III), Ho(III) and Y(III) Complexes of Tiron

B. C. BHUYAN and S. N. DUBEY*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 23 October 1979, accepted 30 December 1979

The formation constants of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complexes of La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, Sm³⁺, Gd³⁺, Tb³⁺, Dy³⁺, Ho³⁺ and Y³⁺ with Tiron have been studied potentiometrically in aqueous medium at different ionic strengths (0.05, 0.1, 0.15 and 0.2M KNO₃) and temperatures (25° and 35°) using Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. In general the stability sequence follows: Ho³⁺ > Dy³⁺ > Y³⁺ > Tb³⁺ > Gd³⁺ > Sm³⁺ > Nd³⁺ > Pr³⁺ > Ce³⁺ > La³⁺. The thermodynamic stability constants, log K₁^{μ=0} and log K₂^{μ=0}, have been determined by extrapolating the values to zero ionic strength. The thermodynamic functions (ΔG, ΔH and ΔS) accompanying complex formation have also been reported.

TIRON is a strong complexing agent and reported to form strong complexes with a number of metal ions¹⁻⁴. From perusal of literature, it is evident that a systematic approach to the complexation reactions of lanthanides with tiron is lacking. The present paper reports the determination of the formation constants for lanthanide complexes at different ionic strengths and temperatures in aqueous medium using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique^{5,6} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷. The thermodynamic stability constants and thermodynamic parameters are determined, and a graphical relationship between thermodynamic stability constants and inverse of ionic radii is depicted.

All the metal nitrate solutions (Rare Earths India Ltd.) were standardized by oxalate method⁸. The other chemicals were of B.D.H., A.R. grade. The solutions were made in doubly distilled water.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand stability constants of Tiron, log K₁^H and log K₂^H, were found to be 12.53, 8.18 (μ=0.05 M, 25°); 12.36, 7.98 (μ=0.1 M, 25°); 12.23, 7.95 (μ=0.15 M, 25°); 12.19, 7.85 (μ=0.2 M, 25°) and 11.94 and 7.79 (μ=0.1 M, 35°), respectively. The formation constants, log K₁, log K₂ and log K₃ were calculated using ligand and chelate titration curves and the values were further refined by different computational techniques^{7,9}. The mean values are given in Table 1.

The general trend in overall stabilities (log β₂ as well as log β₃) of these complexes at 25° and 35°

follows the order :

However in case of Ce(III) it was not possible to determine log K₃ value as n̄ did not exceed 2.2. The decrease in stability (log K₁ and log K₂ values) with increase in ionic strengths and temperature indicates that lowering of the concentrations of indifferent electrolyte and temperature is favourable for complex formation. The thermodynamic stability constants (log K₁^{μ=0} and log K₂^{μ=0}) have been evaluated at the standard state of infinite dilution.

Thermodynamic stability constants (log β₂^{μ=0}) when plotted against inverse of ionic radii (Fig. 1) of the lanthanides showed a reasonably increasing trend in the stabilities of these complexes with an irregularity near Gd³⁺ ion¹⁰.

Fig. 1. Plot of Thermodynamic Stability Constants versus r⁻¹ of Lanthanides.

*To whom correspondence is to be made

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TIRON COMPLEXES AT 25° AND 35°

Stability constants	La ³⁺	Ce ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Tb ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	Ho ³⁺	Y ³⁺
$\mu = 0.05M (25^\circ C)$										
log K ₁	13.82	14.36	14.76	14.96	15.14	15.26	15.34	15.40	15.57	15.07
log K ₂	12.61	13.01	13.36	13.53	13.67	13.90	13.99	14.19	14.43	14.20
log β ₃	26.43	27.37	28.12	28.49	28.81	29.16	29.33	29.59	30.00	29.27
log K ₃	10.20	—	10.52	10.99	11.40	11.86	11.94	12.33	12.71	12.54
log β ₃	36.63	—	38.64	39.48	40.21	41.02	41.27	41.92	42.71	41.81
$\mu = 0.1M (25^\circ C)$										
log K ₁	13.30	13.59	13.98	14.28	14.48	14.53	14.56	14.76	14.86	14.54
log K ₂	12.24	12.54	12.85	13.01	13.20	13.51	13.65	13.79	14.11	13.80
log β ₃	25.54	26.13	26.83	27.29	27.76	28.04	28.21	28.55	28.97	29.34
log K ₃	9.72	—	10.13	10.39	10.64	11.26	11.69	11.97	12.50	11.95
log β ₃	35.26	—	36.96	37.68	38.40	39.30	39.90	40.52	41.47	40.29
$\mu = 0.15M (25^\circ C)$										
log K ₁	13.12	13.50	13.67	14.01	14.22	14.24	14.29	14.48	14.65	14.31
log K ₂	12.07	12.46	12.66	12.90	13.16	13.33	13.42	13.68	13.76	13.57
log β ₃	25.19	25.96	26.33	26.91	27.38	27.57	27.71	28.16	28.41	27.88
log K ₃	10.32	—	10.00	10.59	10.91	11.65	11.95	12.33	12.54	12.15
log β ₃	35.51	—	36.33	37.50	38.29	39.22	39.66	40.49	40.95	40.03
$\mu = 0.2M (25^\circ C)$										
log K ₁	12.94	13.33	13.53	13.68	13.78	13.88	14.03	14.21	14.27	13.86
log K ₂	11.91	12.27	12.53	12.75	12.85	13.07	13.38	13.49	13.63	13.37
log β ₃	24.85	25.60	26.06	26.43	26.63	26.95	27.41	27.70	27.90	27.23
log K ₃	9.98	—	10.38	10.55	10.80	11.45	11.89	12.38	12.53	12.10
log β ₃	34.83	—	36.44	36.98	37.43	38.40	39.30	40.08	40.43	39.33
$\mu = 0.1M (35^\circ C)$										
log K ₁	13.25	13.42	13.76	13.91	14.08	14.24	14.27	14.58	14.82	14.49
log K ₂	12.10	12.48	12.76	12.90	13.05	13.16	13.47	13.68	13.88	13.40
log β ₃	25.35	25.90	26.52	26.81	27.13	27.40	27.74	28.26	28.70	27.89
log K ₃	10.31	—	10.40	10.82	11.14	11.84	12.18	13.09	13.34	12.80
log β ₃	35.66	—	36.92	37.63	38.27	39.24	39.92	41.35	42.04	40.69

The thermodynamic functions (ΔG, ΔH and ΔS) were calculated from the values of log β₂ and log β₃ at different temperatures using standard equations¹¹ and are given in Table 2. The overall changes in the values of ΔH and ΔS for log β₂ indicate that the complexes are both enthalpy and

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF LN³⁺-TIRON COMPLEXES

Ln ³⁺	Free energy change K.cal. mole ⁻¹ (25°C)		Enthalpy change K.cal. mole ⁻¹ (25°C)		Entropy change Cal. mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹ (30°C)	
	-ΔG ₂	-ΔG ₃	-ΔH ₂	-ΔH ₃	ΔS ₂	ΔS ₃
La ³⁺	34.85	48.11	7.99	+16.82	88.59	214.15
Ce ³⁺	35.65	—	9.67	—	85.70	—
Pr ³⁺	36.61	50.43	13.03	1.68	77.75	160.79
Nd ³⁺	37.23	51.41	20.18	2.10	56.24	162.64
Sm ³⁺	37.87	52.39	26.49	5.47	37.56	154.79
Gd ³⁺	38.26	53.62	26.91	2.52	37.44	168.52
Tb ³⁺	38.45	54.43	19.76	+ 0.84	61.77	182.34
Dy ³⁺	38.95	55.28	12.19	+34.89	88.27	297.47
Ho ³⁺	39.53	56.58	11.35	+23.97	92.94	265.69
Y ³⁺	38.67	54.97	18.92	+16.82	65.14	236.80

entropy stabilized. Changes in enthalpy when plotted against inverse of ionic radii placed the lanthanides into two groups with Gd^{3+} as the dividing species¹⁰ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Plot of changes in enthalpy(ΔH) versus r^{-1} .

The positive values of enthalpy (Table 2) suggest that the reactions in the third step are endothermic. A plausible explanation to this effect is that as the ionic size increases the incoming ligand experiences a short of repulsion from the groups already attached with the central ion. However entropy is favourable for complexation as large number of water molecules are set free from the highly hydrated lanthanide ions.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. H.L. Bhatnagar, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University for providing necessary facilities and the U.G.C. for providing teacher-fellowship to one of them (BCB).

References

1. S. N. DUBEY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Less Common Metals*, 1965, **9**, 123.
2. S. N. DUBEY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 685.
3. L. D. SHTENKE, N. A. OKORIK and V. N. KUMOK, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1970, **15**, 1214.
4. SANTOSH D. MAKHIJANI and SATENDRA P. SANGAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15**, 841.
5. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
6. J. BJERRUM, *Metal amine formation in aqueous* (P. Haase and Sons), 1941.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
8. G. B. WANGERT, R. C. WALKER and V. A. STENGER, *Analyst Chem.*, 1932, **24**, 1936.
9. S. N. DUBEY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 327.
10. T. MOELLER, *The Chemistry of Lanthanides*, Pergamon Press, 1973, **24**, 30-32 and references therein.
11. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASIL'EV, *Instability constants of complex compounds*, Pergamon Press, London, 1960, 59-65.